

Impact Screening Summary

This document provides an overview of Impact Screening, an analytical process designed to act as a rapid screening test for the presence of causal impact. It leverages pre-existing data streams containing proxies for increased scalability and speed at the cost of precision. The design objective is to detect whether the treatment cohort exhibits an anomaly in a proxy indicator that is distinct from both its own historical baseline and proximate, similar comparison areas, using percent-change normalization to enable comparison across heterogeneous units.

- Setup
 - Collect treatment cohort inclusion marker, expected impact date, seasonal cycle timeline (e.g. how long it takes seasonality to loop. Annually for seasonal crops, for example), and relevant configuration inputs
 - Gather longitudinal proxy data for the treatment cohort and large set of proximate entities starting a set number (X) of seasonal cycles prior to expected impact (quantity subject to tuning by context, goal is stable baseline)
 - Divide seasonal cycle timeline into equal length intervals of a number of consecutive observations (generally 1-3 based on data fidelity, aggregate observations to factor out noisy data using techniques such as mosaicing if level of fidelity is known)
 - Index each interval by placement in cycle (such as by calendar dates, for cycles oriented to calendar)
 - Exclude entities within a set proximity to the treatment cohort to mitigate spillage risk (where necessary)
 - Group proximate clusters of remaining entities into groups and score by historical similarity to the treatment on weighted composite of correlation and variance; exclude below a calibrated threshold, retaining a minimum of 30 (Control cohorts)
- Measurement
 - For each interval index for each cohort, establish a historical baseline by calculating the median value across that time period from the X pre-impact cycles
 - For each post-impact interval in each cohort, calculate percent change from its index-corresponding historical baseline for the corresponding calendar dates
 - For each post-impact interval, construct a distribution of control percent change from baseline; calculate the out-of-sample percentile for treatment and control cohorts. (Anomaly Level)
- Output
 - Aggregate consecutive post-impact intervals into rolling 4-interval bins; take the 25th percentile of Anomaly Level for each cohort within each window (Normalized Anomaly Level)
 - Construct a distribution of control Normalized Anomaly Levels; calculate the out-of-sample percentile for the treatment cohort (Impact Signal)
 - An Impact Signal above 80% is consistent with plausible non-negligible positive impact; below 80% meaningful impact is unlikely to have occurred at a detectable scale.

- The threshold of minimum detectable impact varies by the similarity of the controls, the strength of the relationship between the outcome and the chosen proxy, and the exactness of the treatment inclusion marker. It is not required to know the exactness or relationship strength in advance.

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